

Systemic Barriers and Resilient Responses: The Livelihood Struggles of Women with Disabilities

Paper Id : 20891 Submission Date : 2025-11-06 Acceptance Date : 2025-11-22 Publication Date : 2025-11-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17760516

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Sansar Chand
Research Scholar
Department Of Social Work
Central University
Kangra, Himachal Pradesh, India,

Sankita Sharma
Research Scholar
Department Of Social Work
Central University
Kangra, Himachal Pradesh, India

Shveta Sharma
Assistant Professor
Department Of Social Work
Central University
Kangra, Himachal Pradesh, India

Abstract

This research was focused on studying the livelihood options being practiced by women with disabilities. This study used the qualitative approach of research in which in-depth interviews were conducted with the women with disabilities of Kangra district to gather the information about the range of economic activities. The data were gathered using in-depth interviews which were useful in gaining the detailed information about their work experience. The study found that Kangra WWDs were overwhelmingly involved in a restricted set of livelihoods, i.e., home-based and informal ones like small-scale cultivation, rearing animals, tailoring, and petty trading. This study found that despite showing considerable resilience, the economic potential of these women remained to a great extent untapped because of institutional constraints.

Keywords

Women with Disabilities (WWDs), Livelihood Options and Nature of Livelihood.

Introduction

Livelihood is the ability, resources (social and physical assets), and activity to earn a living. Women With Disabilities (WWDs) are one amongst the most vulnerable groups. Women with disabilities are double-disadvantaged groups, they face gender discrimination for being women and they also face disability-based exclusion because of their disability. The interaction of WWDs with their environment sometimes bring them in disadvantageous position within school, healthcare, and most importantly, economic opportunities. Although, the Government of India have made various efforts for promoting the equitable access of resources, their inclusion on main stream society, for this Government has introduced various programs, policies and laws from time to time. But still WWDs are one amongst the economically most vulnerable, their participation in the labor market is significantly weaker, and they end up accepting insecure, low-pay, and informal jobs. Kangra district is one of the most populous districts of Himachal Pradesh which has an agriculture, tourism, and service sector-based economy as the main source of economy. The nature of livelihood that they would enjoy would likely be a product of some interaction between their disability, local economic situation, cultural custom, and physical accessibility of the landscape. This research gap calls for a focused exploration of the economic lives of WWDs in this case. This study is thus driven by the following overarching research question: What are the livelihood opportunities available to Women with Disabilities in Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh? Isolation and confinement by culture and traditions, and by attitudes and biases, disproportionately afflict women with disabilities. Women with disabilities isolation results in low esteem and negative emotions. Inadequate support services and lack of proper education led to poor economic status, which further leads to dependency on families or care-givers. Some cultures even go ahead and place blame upon a mother who gives birth to a disabled child, particularly so if the mother is herself a disabled woman. Differently abled women and men may suffer different types of attitudes due to gender discrimination. Although men remain the primary bread-winners and leaders of society, a disabled man, being "less of a man", will not fit the mould (Lonsdale, 1990).

Objective of study

This research was focused on studying the livelihood options being practiced by women with disabilities.

Review of Literature

WWDs are perceived as failing to meet the societal "corporeal standard" for able-bodiedness and femininity (Kumari, 2009). They are stereotyped as incapable of fulfilling traditional roles like wife, mother, and homemaker (Addlakha, 2006; Ghosh, 2010) and are often considered a burden, deprived of decision-making power, and not seen as "woman enough" (WDIN, 2019). This stigma leads to restrictions from families, exclusion from social and religious events, and intense isolation (Mohapatra & Mohanty, 2004; WDIN, 2019). This social exclusion directly fuels economic marginalization. WWDs face significant barriers to education and employment, leading to high rates of illiteracy (as low as 7% in one district), underemployment, and unemployment (D'Souza & Singhe, 2019; WDIN, 2019). When employed, they are often in informal, low-wage work without social security (UNNATI, 2011). A stark gender disparity exists even among disabled

populations, with men with disabilities having a three times higher employment rate (Mitra & Sambamoorthi, 2006), and WWDs earning only 56% of what disabled men earn (Rao, 2004). This enforced financial dependency makes poverty both a cause and a consequence of their disability (Phillipa, 2005). Disabilities are used as an excuse for domestic violence, and they face higher rates of abandonment, widowhood, and forced marriages (Daruwalla et al., 2013; NSSO, 2003). Significant barriers within the justice system, including stigma and inaccessible services, prevent them from reporting abuse or seeking redress (Human Rights Watch, 2018; WDIN, 2019).

Methodology

In this study, the researcher comprised a qualitative study design. This design was deemed the most appropriate as it allowed the researcher to examine in depth the complex and personal phenomenon of the participants' experiences of their livelihood choice, challenges, and aspirations. The study population were the WWDs of Himachal Pradesh's Kangra district. Kangra was selected due to its extensive geographical area, diverse population, and composite economy (combination of agriculture, horticulture, and a growing service sector), which provided an appropriate setting to view diversified livelihood patterns. A non-probability purposive sampling design was used in the selection and recruitment of participants who matched the exact criteria that were the centre of the research aim. The sample population was 35 Women with Disabilities (WWDs).

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Inclusion Criteria:

Should be a woman with a disability (as per the RPWD Act 2016 or holding a disability certificate).

Should be regularly engaged in a livelihood activity for livelihood.

Should be a permanent resident of Kangra district.

Should be of age group 18 to 55 years (including the economically active population).

Data Collection: Data collection primarily used semi-structured in-depth interviews. An interview guide with open-ended questions was prepared to capture themes like:

Type of livelihood activity and nature of work.

Challenges faced (physical, social, financial, institutional).

Aspirations for future livelihood opportunities.

1.1 Types of Livelihood Options	
Livelihood Options performed	Total
Agriculture and Farming	11
Teaching or Academic Work	2
Helper/Cleaner	9
Peon	2
Paper bag making	3
Bamboo Craft	1
Anganwadi helper	2
Nurse	1
Advocate	1
Mid-day meal cooks	1
Tailor	1
Dairy products	1
Total	35

Types of Livelihood Options performed

The findings of the study revealed that Agriculture and Farming (30.56%) and Helper/Cleaner (25.00%) collectively occupy more than 55% of all livelihoods. Agriculture is in line with overall national and international trends whereby a large part of the population in nations like India depends on agriculture even as its contribution to the GDP proportion is decreasing. As explained by Bryceson (2002), agrarian economies

typically have a high concentration of small-scale and subsistence farmers, who are often working with more than one livelihood strategy in order to reduce risk. That there is a high percentage implies this category will likely be in a rural or agrarian setting. The widespread prevalence of "Helper/Cleaner" occupations testifies to the prevalence of the informal economy. This sector is defined by low pay, employment insecurity, and the absence of social security. Chen (2012) thoroughly documents that the informal labor force represents a large, frequently predominant, part of the labor market in developing nations, serving as an indispensable source of revenue for the poor and excluded, frequently without formal education or vocational training. The other livelihoods are dispersed over ten alternate options, each one standing for a small proportion (2.78% to 8.33%). This suggests limited livelihood diversification into stable, skilled, or formal sector employment. A few high-skilled occupations (e.g., Nurse, Advocate, Teacher) and traditional trades (Bamboo Craft, Tailor) indicate a minor but present trend towards skill-based work. Their low frequency, however, highlights the limitation to accessing education and formal vocational training, an issue commonly cited in development discourse (World Bank, 2019). Government-funded programs such as Anganwadi helper and Mid-day meal cook are important social protection and employment generation programs. Their existence, no matter how small, is testimony to the contribution of public policy in offering livelihood assistance, particularly for rural women (Drèze & Khera, 2017). Activities such as Paper bag making (8.33%) and Dairy products (2.78%) are indicative of micro-entrepreneurship and home production. They are commonly taken up as adjustment strategies, notably by women, to earn income towards household needs while juggling household chores.

1.2 Types of Disabilities and Livelihood Options			
Physical Disabilities	Visual Impairment	Hearing Impairment	Speech and Language Disabilities
Agriculture	Agriculture	Advocate	Nurse
Teacher	Peon	Mid-day meal cooks	Make-up artist
Make-up Artist	Paper bag making	Agriculture	Tailor
Helper	Bamboo Craft	Peon	Dairy products
House-help	Anganwadi helper		Helper
Animal rearing (Goat and sheep)			Cleaner

The results of the study revealed a non-random pattern of livelihood activities by disability types, suggesting that the type of disability could influence occupational preference and access.

Physical Disabilities: This group shows the most diversity of livelihood options (6 listed). The types of occupation were a mix of self-employed, skilled, and unskilled (Agriculture, Teacher, Make-up Artist, Helper, House-help, Rearing of Animals). This would mean individuals with physical disabilities are able to employ a wider range of skills, although many of the occupations (Helper, House-help) are in the poorly remunerated informal economy.

Visual Impairment: There are fewer options (5 mentioned) and appear to be concentrated in tactile or routine-based occupations (Agriculture, Paper bag making, Bamboo Craft) and one formal occupation (Peon). The absence of visual acuity demanding occupations (like driving or some machining) is to be expected and demonstrates functional limitations.

Hearing Impairment: This disability has the fewest number of options listed (4), but has a high proportion present in formal or semi-formal streams (Advocate, Peon, Mid-day meal cooks). This perhaps implies that hearing impairment is not such an obstacle where there can be clear sight-based communication (e.g., sign language, written orders) or where the job is routine in nature.

Speech and Language Disabilities: The activities were varied (5 were mentioned) and encompass a range of skilled or entrepreneurial roles (Nurse, Make-up artist, Tailor, Dairy products). This suggests that while communication may be a limitation in some contexts, it does not exclude employment in skilled occupations, particularly manual or independent ones.

Findings

The most significant of the findings was dominance of Agriculture across all disability types. This was cross-supported by international evidence that reveals agriculture to be a significant employer of disabled people in rural areas, generally for the reason that it offers flexible, traditional work within a community framework, albeit not necessarily well remunerated (Mitra & Sambamoorthi, 2014). The trends thus revealed accord significantly with accepted literature in respect of disability and employment:

Limits to Formal Employment: The excessive concentration of work in the informal sector (Helper, Cleaner, House-help, small-scale hand-crafting) is an extensively documented global trend. People with disabilities face serious barriers to formal work in the form of

discrimination, inaccessible environments, and lack of accommodations. They are typically "pushed" into precarious, low-paid informal work as one of few available options (World Health Organization & World Bank, 2011).

Micro-enterprise and Self-Employment Role: The prevalence of livelihoods like Make-up artist, Tailor, Paper bag making, and Dairy products reinforces the importance of micro-enterprise and self-employment. Self-employment is able to offer the independence needed by disabled persons in order to look after their health and work independently, essentially evading discriminatory recruitment processes of the formal labour market (Pagán, 2009).

Mismatch and Underemployment: The figures tend towards potential underemployment. A "Helper" or "Cleaner", for instance, might have the potential for more advanced work but is not able to obtain it due to attitudinal or physical restrictions. Human capital underutilization is a long-standing topic of debate in disability studies (Houtenville & Ruiz, 2012).

Conclusion

Disability-Specific Considerations: The variation between groups supports the idea that labour outcomes differ among all disabilities. Functional impairment is teamed with job requirements. For example, a Hearing Impairment may be less of a barrier for an Advocate who can rely on written text, whereas a Speech and Language Disability may be more of a barrier in that specific occupation but not for a Tailor. The employment choices of individuals with disabilities in this analysis are characterized by a high prevalence in agriculture, a significant contribution of the informal economy, and a favourable though small contribution of skilled self-employment. The trend differs sharply by disability category, a reflection of the interaction of functional capability and the demands of a job. These findings emphasize the need for intensive vocational training schemes, encouragement of mainstream employers to employ disabled individuals, and support for disabled entrepreneurs in establishing their micro-enterprises as successful businesses.

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